

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF GRAFTED POLYMER CONFORMATIONS ON NANOPARTICLES BY RAFT POLYMERIZATION

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SUMMARY

Prior work has shown that the grafting of polymer chains onto spherical nanofillers can be used to control the dispersion and morphology of the nanoparticles. To optimize this control, it would be beneficial to understand the behavior of polymer brushes on spherical surfaces. A set of silica particles with grafted polystyrene chains ranging in molecular weight from 5 to 120 kg/mol and with graft densities of 0.05, 0.39, and 0.55 ch/nm² were synthesized and the brush height was measured by dynamic light scattering. It was found that as predicted by theory, the brush height scales as $N^{4/5}$ in the stretched brush regime and is the first clear evidence of a transition to semi-dilute behavior at high molecular weight. Single chain mean field modeling confirms the experimental stretched brush intermediate 4/5 exponent at these particle curvatures. As the core radius is increased, the scaling relationship gradually shifts toward unity, a result predicted by prior theoretical work. Small angle neutron scattering (SANS) of grafted hydrogenated PS on silica nanoparticles in deuterated PS matrices reveal the brush height of these interfaces in actual composite systems, giving insights into the properties of nanocomposite grafted interfaces.

Keywords: RAFT, grafted chain(s), polymer brush(es), nanoparticle(s), hybrid nanoparticle, DLS

INTRODUCTION

Polymers grafted to surfaces, also known as polymer brushes, have gained recent interest with the advent of advanced living radical polymerization (LRP) methods [1]. Previously, the graft density was limited to relatively low surface coverage with “grafting to” approaches; the grafted chains hindered the additional attachment of polymer chains. With LRP methods, a “grafting from” approach allowed chains to be polymerized from a surface-initiated site, which enabled much greater surface coverage since steric blocking of the surface was no longer an impediment.

Since their inception, decades ago, polymer brush behavior has been modeled in solution under a variety of solvent conditions. For brushes on flat surfaces in a good solvent, the pioneering work of Alexander [2] and de Gennes [3] found that the brush height, h , (thickness of the brush layer) scales with the degree of polymerization, N , (l_0 is the monomer length and σ is the graft density) as described by Equation 1.

$$h \sim l_o N \sigma^{1/3} \quad (1)$$

This scaling relationship has been experimentally verified for flat interfaces. As curvature of the grafted surface is introduced, the scaling relationship represents the asymptotic limit as the curvature is decreased (increasing radii of curvature, r_o). Daoud and Cotton [4] expanded the scaling arguments of Alexander and de Gennes to incorporate surfaces of cylindrical and spherical curvature. The brush height was found to behave according to Equation 2 for spherical curvatures in good solvents.

$$h \sim N^{3/5} \sigma^{1/5} r_o^{2/5} \quad (2)$$

The 3/5 exponent corresponds to the Flory exponent in good solvent. However, this scaling behavior remains valid only for extremely large curvatures. Self-consistent field theory predictions by Dan and Tirrell [5] showed that the scaling of brush height with N varied from Eqn. 2 to Eqn. 1 as the particle radius increased. The curvature-dependent exponent represents an intermediate scaling relationship between behaviors. Eqn. 2 represents the semi-dilute polymer brush behavior, where chains maximize solvent-chain interactions by stretching away from the surface, but are not strongly stretched. The intermediate exponent indicates an enhanced degree of stretching, termed the “highly stretched” brush.

Current theoretical computations using single chain mean-field theory verifies that this intermediate power law is a consequence of finite particle radius. The transition from stretched to the SDPB occurs because the volume available to the chain increases with increasing distance from the surface, thus allowing for an efficient decrease in chain packing frustration.

There are then three general behaviors that can be expected of most spherical and densely grafted brushes. First, at very low molecular weights, the grafted chains are too short to interact and form “mushrooms” on the surface. As the chains grow, the “mushrooms” overlap and steric crowding causes the chains to extend away from the surface. This second behavior is the highly stretched brush regime, where steric crowding forces chains to be effectively confined to a conical region extending away from the surface. Finally, at high enough molecular weight, the chains extend far enough away from the surface to regain their freedom from the crowding of adjacent chains. This third behavior is the SDPB regime where chains behave akin to Flory radius scaling as in Eqn. 2.

These expected behaviors reveal two transitions of interest, the “mushroom” to stretched brush transition, and the stretched brush to SDPB transition. The former is calculated by a simple criterion for when the “mushrooms” overlap, namely $\sigma R_g^2 \approx 1.2$ [6]. The latter transition has been attempted to be described by an “effective graft density” for when lateral chain constraint is alleviated, which has been postulated to occur at ~ 0.05 ch/nm². [7]

To test these behaviors and the transitional predictions requires the ability to precisely control the graft density and molecular weight of grafted chains on the surface of highly monodisperse particles. The current study uses nearly monodisperse silica nanoparticles (14±4 nm) grafted with polystyrene using reversible addition fragmentation chain transfer (RAFT) polymerization [8,9] Using this technique, polymer brushes with varying chain lengths and graft densities were synthesized, ranging from ~5-120 kg/mol in molecular weight with polydispersities less than 1.2, and 0.05-0.55 ch/nm² in surface graft density (shown in Table 1). With dynamic light scattering (DLS), the dimensions of the polymer brush are capable of being measured and can then be compared to theoretical predictions. This experimental study is the

broadest of its kind to date and is capable of examining the diverse behaviors exhibited by grafted polymers on spherical nanoparticles[7, 10].

Table 1: Range of specimens prepared by surface-initiated RAFT polymerization for this study, along with the corresponding brush height as measured by DLS.

Graft Density σ (ch/nm^2)	Molecular Weight M_W (kg/mol)	PDI (M_W/M_N)	Brush Height h (nm)	St. Dev. (nm)
0.05	34	1.05	27.98	2.90
0.05	52	1.06	41.82	3.25
0.05	95	1.10	59.75	9.55
0.39	4	1.06	6.37	0.82
0.39	6.6	1.08	9.61	6.59
0.39	13	1.06	18.02	2.24
0.39	45	1.05	49.33	2.35
0.39	74	1.10	67.31	3.40
0.39	114	1.13	91.40	2.81
0.55	26	1.06	37.61	2.38
0.55	59	1.08	66.42	2.98
0.55	77	1.09	75.89	6.41
0.55	117	1.12	100.26	6.36

Measurements of the brush height while in a polymer matrix are an altogether more difficult challenge to obtain information experimentally. Staining the brush prior to incorporation of a chemically identical matrix will provide contrast for TEM microscopy. In doing so, however, the natural conformation of the grafted chains will be altered by the reaction and presence of the staining molecules. In addition, the microtoming process introduces additional error due to potential deformation and the thickness limitations of the specimen. Small angle neutron scattering (SANS) of hydrogenated brushes in deuterated matrices (or deuterated brushes in hydrogenated matrices) is capable of providing the necessary contrast while maintaining both the “natural” chain conformations of grafted chains, as well as maintaining chemical homogeneity across the interface. This ensures that the interactions remain entropic.

The current work also includes measurements of the grafted layer thickness in a free-polymer environment (in a composite) and in the absence of any solvent. These “dry” conditions probe the behavior of grafted chains as they would be utilized in a composite. For this study, the same silica-g-PS hybrid nanoparticles used in the DLS study are dispersed in deuterated PS matrices

METHODS

Theory

The single chain mean-field approach considers a single chain for which all the intramolecular interactions are exactly taken into account. Previous work has shown that this approach is superior to the Dolan-Edwards self-consistent field theory in that it provides better agreement with simulations (and presumably experiments) [11]. The intermolecular interactions are represented by a mean field of the interactions with the chain’s environment. The theory calculates the thermodynamic properties of such a system by evaluating the probability distribution function (PDF), $P(a)$, of chain conformations, along with the distribution of solvent molecules around the interface. The PDF and solvent distribution are found by minimizing the system’s free energy subject to a volume filling constraint. Obtaining the PDF and solvent density

distribution then allows for relevant thermodynamic properties, such as the free energy or chemical potential, to be calculated (see Appendix for more details).

Synthesis

The RAFT polymerization process is described in detail elsewhere [8,9] and is briefly discussed here. Silica nanoparticles (14±4 nm, Nissan Chemical, 30wt% in MEK) were dispersed in THF, grafted with a silane coupling agent, and reacted with the chain transfer agent. UV-vis absorption spectra were acquired and the particles were then dried and weighed. Particles were re-dispersed in Tetrahydrofuran (HPLC Grade, Acros Organics) and then surface-polymerized with styrene monomer (ACS grade, Acros Organics) that was passed through a neutral alumina column to remove the inhibitor. After polymerization, a sample of grafted chains was cleaved from the surface using HF, whereupon the polymer molecular weight was determined by GPC using a polystyrene standard.

Characterization

The grafted particle solution was re-dissolved in benzene (ACS grade, Acros Organics) and diluted to ~0.05 mg/mL. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements (Dynapro Titan, Wyatt Technologies Inc., Santa Barbara, CA) were performed on ten different aliquots of the diluted solutions to obtain the average hydrodynamic radius. The determination of particle size by dynamic light scattering is well documented in the literature and consequently will not be discussed here.

Additional samples were prepared for small angle neutron scattering (SANS) experiments. Silica nanoparticles (15nm) were grafted at 0.05 ch/nm² with 30 and 130 kg/mol of hydrogenated PS. The resulting particles were mixed at different loadings (5 and 15 wt % silica) with a 90 or 200 kg/mol deuterated matrix. Since the neutron scattering length density of silica is relatively close to the hydrogenated PS (2x10¹⁰ and 1.5x10¹⁰ cm⁻² respectively), SANS essentially measures the combined size of the particle and grafted chains.

SANS was performed at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) with neutrons of 6Å wavelength. The wavevector, q , was varied from 0.0033 – 0.5 Å⁻¹. The data were corrected for background, empty cell scattering, and detector efficiency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theory

Figure 1a shows the results of h for a radius of 5 monomer units plotted in a form inspired by eq. 2. The mostly linear behavior seen in the plot indicates that the scaling laws perform well for both of the modeled chains across a wide range of grafting densities. There is only a slight difference in the scaling with N for chains with excluded volume (“SAW”) or no excluded volume (“Markov”) for intramolecular interactions. (Interchain excluded volume is enforced in all cases through the device of the incompressibility constraint.)

Figure 1 – The scaling behavior of self-avoiding walk (solid symbols) and Markovian chains (open symbols) for a sphere of radius 5 (a) and 15 (b). The results are obtained for grafting densities of 0.1 (circles), 0.2 (squares), 0.3 (diamonds), 0.4 (up-turned triangles) and 0.5 (down-turned triangles).

For example, for a grafting density of 0.3, the brush height scales with $N^{0.61}$ for Markov chains, and $N^{0.62}$ for SAW. Despite the similarity in the N scaling, the SAW chains show better agreement with eq. 2 as indicated by the reduced scatter of the SAW calculations as compared to the Markovian. This scaling behavior is indicative of SDPB behavior. In Figure 1b the same scaling behavior is examined for an interface with a radius of 15 monomer units. As in Figure 1a, there is a slight difference in the scaling behavior of the SAW ($\sim N^{0.78}$) and Markovian ($\sim N^{0.76}$) chains. For a slight increase in particle radius, the behavior of the chains is altered and represents the intermediate scaling regime. There is a noticeable decrease in the accuracy of the scaling predictions for this radius. In this case, the data points are less linear and are less precise than those which were obtained for a smaller radius, and N no longer scales with the predicted value (the brush height shifts towards the planar case where $h \sim N$).

These results are in agreement with previous simulation studies [12] that have shown that the scaling regime begins to break down as radius is increased. This is likely due to the qualitative shift in the density profile, as the scaling is likely valid when the profile is concave down, but begins breaking down when the density profile begins to resemble that of flat interfaces.

Experimental Results: DLS

The brush height, h , is simply the difference between the hydrodynamic radius of the polymer grafted particle, R_h , and the core radius, r_o . The brush height as a function of degree of polymerization, N , is shown in Figure 2a for the samples in Table 1. Curve fits of the stretched brush regime and eqn. 2 are labeled.

Figure 2 – (a) The brush height vs. degree of polymerization with the curve fits of eqn. 2 indicated. (b) A log-log plot of the graft density-normalized brush height versus degree of polymerization, N . Two behavioral regimes are plotted - stretched brushes follow $N^{4/5}$, while SDPB brushes follow $N^{3/5}$. Red circles are 0.05, green diamonds are 0.39, blue squares are 0.55, gray triangles are 0.59 [from 10], and half-filled boxes are 0.7 ch/nm^2 [from 7].

The stretched regime exists at low molecular weights for each graft density. The transition to SDPB behavior is a function of graft density. At lower graft densities, the crowding caused by adjacent chains is alleviated at smaller distances from the particle surface.

When the data are plotted in a log-log form inspired by eqn. 2, as in Figure 2b, along with the previous data in the literature [7, 10], several things become apparent. First, almost all of the data from the current study (except those at the lowest graft density), the data of Savin et al. [10] and of Ohno et al. [7], fall on an apparently “universal” curve when plotted as a function of $\sigma^{1/5}$. This is consistent with σ scaling in good solvent semi-dilute brush conditions. However, most of the data in the three sets apparently follow a power law scaling of $h \sim N^{4/5}$. At the same curvature, the experiments match the predicted behavior of the single-chain mean field modeling, where $h \sim N^{0.78}$. A similar conclusion was presented by Ohno et al. [7], who suggested that their data are well fit by a power law exponent of 0.83. Their data, which are clearly in the stretched regime, thus point to the fact that the brush height scales as $h \sim N^{4/5}$ in this regime for particle radii between 7 and 65 nm. Dan and Tirrell’s [5] solution of the Dolan-Edwards SCF model shows that the h scaling with N is radius dependent, ranging from 3/5 (which corresponds to bulk behavior) for very small particles, to 1 for a planar brush. The 4/5 scaling obtained from these results thus reflects an intermediate scaling representative of finite curvature particles.

Second, not all of the data in Fig. 2b fall on the “universal” curve which is defined by a N scaling power law of 4/5. The data for the lowest graft density (0.05 chains/nm²) appear to not follow this scaling as well as the other data, as seen from the deviation from the 4/5 curve in Fig. 2a. This point will be explored in more detail below.

a) b)
 Figure 3 – The experimentally determined brush height is normalized by the expected brush height in the stretched (3a) and SDPB (3b) regimes. Where the solid colored lines intersect unity in Figure 3a indicates the approximate transition point from stretched to SDPB behavior. The key is identical to that of Figure 2.

To illustrate the differences in behavior, in Fig. 3a, the brush height is normalized by the predicted value from the scaling relationship $h \sim N^{4/5}$, which is termed h_s . At low N values this ratio is essentially unity. However, in all cases, the data begin to deviate below 1 at larger molecular weights. The extrapolated N value where this deviation begins decreases with decreasing σ . This deviation is identified as the crossover where the chain behavior changes from stretched brush to SDPB. It is expected that the SDPB curve should yield lower h than the stretched brush for large N . In an apparently contradictory extrapolation, this then yields that the SDPB must yield larger h values for smaller N , a result that is exemplified in Fig. 3b. This is because the SDPB brush height is growing not from the surface, but on top on an already existing stretched brush layer and thus while the net change in brush height is smaller than it would be for a stretched brush, the overall brush height behavior is larger than that for a brush entirely in the SDPB regime.

The data for 0.55 ch/nm^2 lies above unity in Figure 3a at lower molecular weights. This apparent discrepancy is merely a result of the normalization by h_s . The average brush height data used for the normalization deviate slightly above this prediction (within the limits of the error bars) at lower molecular weights and therefore yield a larger than unity value. Before proceeding with the conclusion that the stretched brush regime is observed, it is important to be convinced that the low N data indeed follow the stretched behavior and exclude the possibility of mushroom behavior.

For any graft density, the chains assume “mushroom” like conformations if they are very short and thus do not interact laterally with other chains. Recent work by Chen et al. [6] have suggested that the chain lengths beyond the inequality $\sigma R_g^2 \leq 1.2$ will cause chains to be beyond the “mushroom” regime. For a graft density of 0.39 chains/nm^2 , for which the most comprehensive data exists, this suggests that all chains shorter than ~ 30 monomers will not be extended. Since the chain lengths studied for this grafting density clearly exceed this criterion, and further show that $h \sim h_s$, it can be concluded that the scaling $h \sim N^{4/5}$ does indeed correspond to the stretched regime rather than the “mushroom” regime.

For the 0.39 ch/nm^2 data longer than 400 monomers, it is apparent from Fig. 3a that the brush height no longer follows this stretched scaling. This deviation corresponds to

the high N transition from stretched to SDPB scaling due to the reduced crowding of the brushes. To give credence to the fact that this second regime is the SDPB regime, in Fig 3b h normalized by its SDPB value, h_{SDPB} , from eq. 2 is plotted. Clearly, at large N the data converge to a value of unity, verifying the proposed scenario.

Extending these scaling ideas to a graft density of 0.05 chains/nm² suggests that all chains shorter than 80 monomers will not be extended. Since the extrapolated transition to the SDPB appears to occur for chains as small as ~ 100 , at this graft density the stretched brush behavior is never reached. The chains at this grafting density are always in the SDPB regime, verified by Fig. 3b.

Thus, the data support the notion that there are two regimes where the chains do not behave akin to stretched brushes. For surface grafting densities small enough to eliminate the possibility of chain crowding, and for longer chains beyond r_t the increased volume available per chain creates the second regime. The former is found in both flat and curved brushes whilst the latter is exclusively caused by the curvature of the particles. Thus, with the large particle curvature and low graft density of 0.05 ch/nm², the possibility of stretched behavior is excluded at any molecular weight.

This implies that there is a critical graft density that defines when stretched behavior does and does not occur. This critical graft density will be a function of the particle curvature. From the data presented here, for 14 nm particles this critical graft density lies between 0.05 and 0.39 ch/nm², an observation consistent with prior works [7]. These results show the diverse behavior of grafted polymer systems [13].

Experimental Results: SANS

The SANS scattered intensity, $I(q)$, is analyzed using a simplified Beaucage model [14], given by equation 3,

$$I(q) = B \left[\frac{1}{q} \right]^p + C \exp \left[-\frac{q^2 R_g^2}{3} \right] + D \left[\frac{\text{erf} \left(q R_g / \sqrt{6} \right)}{q} \right]^q \quad (3)$$

where B, C, D, and p are fitting parameters, q is the scattering vector, R_g is the radius of gyration. By subtracting the core size from the calculated radius of gyration, the thickness of the grafted layer is obtained. Table 2 shows the characteristics of the polymer brushes and matrices used in the SANS study.

Table 2: Characteristics of the grafted polymer layer, matrix, and particle loading of the SANS specimens used in this study.

Graft Density (ch/nm ²)	Graft MW (kg/mol)	Matrix MW (kg/mol)	Graft/Matrix MW's	Particle Loading (%)	R_g (Å)	Graft Layer Thickness (nm)
0.26	130	90	1.44	15	169	9.4
0.26	130	90	1.44	5	191	11.6
0.26	30	90	0.33	15	118	4.3
0.26	30	90	0.33	5	159	8.4
0.26	130	200	0.65	15	119	4.4

Figure 4 – Thickness of the grafted layer as a function of matrix solvent quality for (A) different particle loadings with a constant matrix molecular weight of 90k, and (B) constant graft molecular weight with varied matrix molecular weight at 15 wt.% silica loading. Ideal melt coil behavior is indicated as a dashed line for the respective grafted molecular weights.

The thickness of the grafted layer is plotted against the ratio of the grafted molecular weight to the matrix molecular weight in Figure 4. This ratio is a measure of the solvent quality; longer chains will be poorer solvents, while shorter chains will be good solvents. Therefore larger ratios (>1) will represent better solvents, while small ratios (<1) indicate poorer solvents.

While an incomplete data set, these results show several key points. First, in Figure 4a, the brush height is a function of particle loading. Thus, at high loadings, when the particles are in contact, the brush height decreases. Additionally, at lower loadings, the better the solvent quality, the more extended the brush is from the particle surface.

In Figure 4b, the matrix molecular weight is varied at a fixed particle loading of 15 wt.% silica. In the presence of higher molecular weight matrices, the polymer brush shrinks beyond the predicted value of ideal coils for bulk density polystyrene. The unfavorable wettability of the 130k brush by the matrix polymer results in an increase in density of the polymer chains compared to the bulk. The density increase is inconsistent with previous modeling expectations [15], where the density near the surface was shown to decrease upon filler addition. This discrepancy is likely a result of the grafted interface and resulting inability for chains to orient tangential to the surface.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The intermediate scaling in the stretched regime of $h \sim N^{4/5}$ using single-chain mean field theory is a result of the core particle curvature alone, and is verified by DLS experiments on polymer brushes. Over a range of polymer chain lengths, grafting densities, and core particle sizes, the experimental results demonstrate that the height of a stretched polymer brush displays an intermediate, core radius dependent, scaling relationship with the degree of polymerization. The power law is likely to vary between $3/5$ and 1 , corresponding to bulk and flat interface behaviors, depending upon the core particle curvature. Smaller particles will exhibit scaling exponents approaching $3/5$, whilst those for larger particles will approach unity – a result that has been predicted from theoretical models.

There is a transition between stretched and SDPB behavior, which occurs when a chain becomes long enough that its radius-dependent available volume allows for a reduction of the packing frustration. For semi-dilute brushes, the theoretical prediction of $h \sim N^{3/5}$ matches the experimental observations of high N SDPB behavior. These results are shown to be applicable to a wide experimental range of brush parameters that also include the currently existing experimental data reported in literature. Brushes initially scale with the intermediate relationship of $h \sim N^{4/5}$ in the stretched brush regime, and then deviate from this behavior as the molecular weight increases, entering the SDPB regime.

Finally, it is proposed that there must exist a critical graft density, which varies with particle curvature, below which stretched behavior is excluded at all molecular weights. This is evidenced by the overlap of the low N “mushroom” behavior and the high N transition from stretched to SDPB. This critical value appears to occur between 0.05 and 0.39 ch/nm².

SANS experiments on hydrogenated brushes in deuterated matrices have shown that the matrix can be thought of as a solvent whose quality is determined qualitatively by the ratio of the brush molecular weight to the matrix molecular weight. The wettability of the brush has a dramatic effect on the size of the grafted layer. Poorer solvent quality (larger matrix chains) results in poorer wetting conditions and compacts the brush chains beyond their bulk density. Specimens with better solvent quality are more swollen since the matrix is capable of penetrating further into the brush, displacing the grafted chains and causes them to extend further into the matrix. As the particle loading is increased, the proximity of adjacent grafted particles also has an effect on the brush extension. At higher loadings, the brush is constrained by the close proximity of adjacent grafted particles and presumably induces an overall reduction in chain extension.

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References

1. Tsujii, Y.; Ohno, K.; Yamamoto, S. et al. *Adv. Polym. Sci.* **2006**, 197, 1-45 and references therein
2. Alexander, S. *J. Phys.* **1977**, 38, 983-987
3. de Gennes, P. *Macromolecules* **1980**, 13, 1069-1075
4. Daoud, M.; Cotton, J. *J. Phys.* **1982**, 43, 531-538
5. Dan, N.; Tirrell, M. *Macromolecules* **1992**, 25, 2890-2895
6. Chen, W.Y.; Zheng, J.X.; Cheng, S.Z.D. et al. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2004**, 93, 028301
7. Ohno, K.; Morinaga, T.; Takeno, S. et al. *Macromolecules* **2007**, 40, 9143-9150
8. Li, C.; Benicewicz, B. C. *Macromolecules* **2005**, 38, 5929-5936
9. Li, C., Han, J., Ryu, C. Y., et al. *Macromolecules* **2006**, 39, 3175-3183
10. Savin, D.; Pyun, J.; Patterson, G. et al. *J. Polym. Sci. B: Polym. Phys.* **2002**, 40, 2667-2676
11. Avalos, J. P.; Mackie, A. D.; Diez-Orrite, S. *Macromolecules* **2004**, 37, 1143-1151
12. Toral, R.; Chakrabarti, A. *Phys. Rev. E* **1993**, 47, 4240-4246.

13. Akcora, P.; Liu, H.; Kumar, S. K., et al. *Nat. Mat.* **2009**, 8, 354-359
14. Beaucage, G.; Kammler, H.; Pratsinis, S. E. *J. Appl. Cryst.* **2004**, 37, 523-535
15. Vacatello, M. *Macromol. Theory Simul.* **2002**, 11, 53-57; Termonia, Y. *Polymer* **2009**, 50, 1062-1066
16. Szleifer, I.; Benshaul, A.; Gelbart, W. M. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1985**, 83, 3612-3620.
17. Carignano, M. A.; Szleifer, I. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1995**, 102, 8662-8669.
18. Mackie, A. D.; Panagiotopoulos, A. Z.; Szleifer, I. *Langmuir* **1997**, 13, 5022-5031.
19. Guerin, C. B. E.; Szleifer, I. *Langmuir* **1999**, 15, 7901-7911.

APPENDIX

Single chain mean-field approach for curved brushes

The single chain mean field approach was developed in order to study the aggregation of amphiphiles in vacuum [16, 17] and was later generalized to the formation of micelles in solvent [18, 19]. This work will consider a variety of systems containing a number of chains of length n end tethered to both spherical and flat interfaces. Chain lengths of 10 to 100 segments and radii of 5 to 50 statistical segment lengths will be considered. The quantity r represents the radial distance of the quantity of interest from the center of a sphere of radius R . The grafting density σ represents the number of polymer chains, N_p , per unit area of the interface.

The SCMF approach considers a single chain for which all the intermolecular interactions are exactly taken into account. The intermolecular interactions are represented by the mean field of the interactions of the chain's environment. The theory calculates the thermodynamic properties of such a system by evaluating the probability distribution function (PDF), $P(a)$, of chain conformations, along with the distribution of solvent molecules around the interface. An individual chain conformation, given by a , is given by the bond sequence and angles of the chain segments. The chains are allowed free rotation, and bond angles are not constrained. The PDF and solvent distribution are found by minimizing the system's free energy subject to a volume filling constraint. Obtaining the PDF and solvent density distribution then allows for relevant thermodynamic properties, such as the free energy or chemical potential, to be calculated.

The SCMF approach considers the polymer/solvent system surrounding the interface to be incompressible, such that a constant fluid density is maintained. The system is homogenous for all distances that are parallel to the interface (for both curved and flat surfaces) such that the only distance of interest is r . In order to maintain a constant fluid density, a volume constraint is required such that

$$\langle \phi_p(r) \rangle + \langle \phi_s(r) \rangle = 1 \quad (1)$$

where f is the volume fraction at distance r from the nanoparticle surface. The volume fraction also represents the probability of finding a segment of the appropriate type at distance r . The subscripts p and s refer to chain and solvent, respectively. The volume fractions given in equation (1) can be described in terms of the number of molecules and volume at each distance r . In terms of these quantities, the constraint is given by

$$\frac{\sigma \sum_{\alpha} P(\alpha) n_p(\alpha, r) v_p}{V(r)} + \frac{N_s(r) v_s}{V(r)} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where n_p is the number of segments in a polymer chain, v_i is the volume of a surfactant chain segment or solvent molecule, and $V(r)$ is the volume occupied up to distance r .

An expression for the Helmholtz free energy is required in order to evaluate $P(a)$:

$$\beta W = \sigma \sum_{\alpha} P(\alpha) (\ln P(\alpha)) + \int_R^{\infty} \frac{\langle \phi_s(r) \rangle V(r)}{v_s} (\ln \langle \phi_s(r) \rangle - \beta \mu_s - 1) dr \quad (3)$$

The first expression of the right hand side of equation (3) is the conformational entropy of the grafted chains and the second term is the entropic contribution to the free energy of mixing of the solvent molecules. The next step consists of minimizing the free energy subject to the previously described packing constraint by the introduction of Lagrange multipliers, given by $\beta\pi(r)$. The minimization of the free energy provides the functional forms of the PDF of chain conformations and the density profiles of the solvent molecules. Minimizing the free energy with respect to $P(a)$ subject to the packing constraint yields

$$P(\alpha) = \frac{1}{q} e^{-\int_R^{\infty} \beta\pi(r) n_p(r, \alpha) v_p dr} \quad (4)$$

where q is a normalization constant such that $\sum_{\alpha} P(\alpha) = 1$. The solvent density profile is given by

$$\langle \phi_s(r) \rangle = e^{-\beta\pi(r) v_s} \quad (5)$$

The quantity $\beta\pi(r)$ is the osmotic pressure necessary to maintain a constant chemical potential across all distances from the nanoparticle and can be found by replacing the above forms of the PDF and solvent density profile in the constraint equation. The surfactant PDF and solvent density profile can then be substituted into the free energy expression, which reduces to

$$\beta W = -\sigma \ln q - \int \beta\pi(r) V(r) dr \quad (6)$$

The values of $p(r)$ are the only unknowns required to determine the PDF, and therefore, the thermodynamic properties of the system. The multipliers are calculated by solving for the PDF and the solvent and chain density profiles, as will be discussed below. The calculation requires only the chain conformations and the number of chains grafted to the interface as input.

In order to solve equation (1), the space must be discretized into concentric layers of thickness d . For conformation a the number of segments within volume element dr is replaced by the number of segments within layer i :

$$\int n(r, \alpha) dr = n(i, \alpha) \quad (7)$$

This scheme is applied to the previous equations, which can then be used to solve for the discrete lateral pressures, $p(i)$. The PDF becomes

$$P(\alpha) = \frac{1}{q} e^{-\sum_i^M \pi'(i) n_p(i, \alpha) \frac{v_p}{v_s}} \quad (8)$$

where $n_p(i)$ is the number of segments in layer i , M is the total number of layers, and π' is defined as $\beta\pi v_s$. The solvent density profile is now

$$\langle \phi_s(i) \rangle = e^{-\pi'(i)} \quad (9)$$

The free energy is now given by

$$\beta W = -\sigma \ln q - \sum_i^M \frac{\pi'(i)V(i)}{v_s} \quad (10)$$

and the constraint equation is rewritten as

$$1 = e^{-\pi'(i)} + \frac{\sigma}{V(i)} \sum_{\alpha} \frac{n_p(\alpha, i)v_p}{q} e^{-\sum_i^M \pi'(i)n_p(i, \alpha) \frac{v_c}{v_s}} \quad (11)$$

Chain conformations are generated using the rotational isomeric states (RIS) chain model. This model is characterized by bonds having three equally possible states: trans, gauche+ and gauche-. Chain conformations are generated using a random sampling method and after a conformation is generated, the segments are verified as self avoiding; however, if there is overlap between any segments the conformation is discarded and a replacement conformation is generated. This last step is ignored when generating Markovian chain conformations. For the results shown in the following section 5000000 chain conformations are generated, and 40 layers ($M = 40$) are included in the calculations. Increasing the number of layers has no impact on the results as long as bulk conditions are reached.